

CHATGPT: THE PROMISE AND LIMITATIONS OF OPEN AI'S GROUNDBREAKING CHATBOT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10391071>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 05-December 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 10- December 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 15- December 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

language model, reinforcement, verbosity, limitations, accountability frameworks, initiated efforts, exploring mechanisms, public input, responsible implementation

ABSTRACT

This scientific article provides an extensive evaluation of ChatGPT, an advanced language model developed by OpenAI. With the ability to generate coherent and contextually relevant responses, ChatGPT has garnered significant attention for its potential to revolutionize human-computer interactions. However, we also shed light on the limitations and ethical concerns associated with such technology to initiate a discussion on its responsible implementation

Introduction:

OpenAI's ChatGPT, the sibling model of GPT-3, is an AI chatbot trained in conversational data and designed to provide human-like responses to user inputs. In this article, we investigate the capabilities of ChatGPT along with its potential applications, ethical implications, and areas for further improvement.

1. Overview of ChatGPT:

ChatGPT operates on a large-scale language model, trained using Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) and fine-tuned through an interactive process with human AI trainers. This approach enables the model to generate responses based on both its existing knowledge and human-like conversational behavior.

2. Strengths and Applications:

ChatGPT has demonstrated remarkable capabilities in generating coherent answers, refining prompts, and providing suggestions for a wide range of topics. It holds tremendous potential for customer service, language tutoring, and information retrieval, where it can assist users in finding relevant information with ease.

3. Limitations and Challenges:

Despite its impressive performance, ChatGPT suffers from several limitations. These include: generating incorrect or nonsensical responses, sensitivity to input phrasing, verbosity, lack of clarification-seeking behavior, and potential biases inherited from the training data. Additionally, it may struggle to acknowledge its own limitations or respond to unexpected queries accurately.

4. Responsible Implementation and Ethical Concerns:

Responsible deployment of AI technologies like ChatGPT necessitates addressing ethical considerations associated with potential misuse. Precautions must be taken to prevent the amplification of biases, spreading misinformation, or deploying the technology in contexts that could manipulate or deceive individuals. Transparency and accountability frameworks need to be developed to maintain trust and ensure user safety.

5. Future Directions and Improvements:

OpenAI recognizes the limitations of ChatGPT and is actively working towards mitigating them. The organization has initiated efforts to gather public input on deployment policies, exploring mechanisms to allow users to customize the system's behavior while avoiding malicious uses.

Conclusion:

ChatGPT represents a significant leap forward in natural language processing and has vast potential to transform various domains. However, its limitations, such as generating nonsensical responses and susceptibility to biases, must be carefully addressed to avoid unintended consequences. A comprehensive approach that prioritizes responsible development, ethical considerations, and ongoing user feedback will be essential for ChatGPT to deliver on its promise as a powerful and trusted conversational AI tool.

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